

Cultivar ADT36 was grown during Jun-Oct 1986. Plot size was 25 m² in a split-plot design replicated 3 times. Soil was clayey loam with pH 7 and CEC 36 meq/ 100 g. It had 0.13% total N,

70 kg available P/ha, and 92 kg exchangeable K/ ha. Maximum and minimum temperatures during growth were 31-39 °C and 22-28 °C. Total rainfall was 324 mm.

Split application of *A. brasilense* inoculum through seed, seedling, and soil gave the highest grain and straw yields, plant height, and number of productive tillers (see table).□

Effect of urea on decomposition of azolla

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We applied urea as a foliar spray over the azolla mat in a pot culture experiment to study azolla decomposition. One liter soil extract

medium was kept in plastic tubs and 30 g *Azolla pinnata*, *A. microphylla*, and *A. filiculoides* inoculated and maintained. Urea was added directly to the soil extract solution at 50, 100, 250, 500, 1,000, and 2,000 ppm or sprayed at 3 d after inoculation.

At 5 d after urea treatment, the decayed biomass was filtered in muslin and the moisture content removed by placing the mass on tissue paper.

With increased urea concentration,

azolla decomposition increased (see table). Urea at 2,000 ppm caused considerable weight reduction in all the 3 species of azolla. Weight reduction was highest in *A. microphylla*. Urea incorporated into the soil extract significantly activated decomposition (see figure).□

Influence of foliar spray of urea on the decomposition of azolla. Tamil Nadu, India.

Urea concentration (ppm)	Weight on 5th day after spraying					
	<i>A. pinnata</i>		<i>A. filiculoides</i>		<i>A. microphylla</i>	
	g	% decrease from initial inoculum	g	% decrease from initial inoculum	g	% decrease from initial inoculum
50	13.7	54	20.8	31	18.1	40
100	12.8	57	20.0	33	15.4	49
250	11.2	63	18.0	40	15.0	50
500	14.8	51	15.9	47	12.5	58
1000	13.3	56	13.9	54	10.5	65
2000	10.8	64	12.0	60	10.0	67
CD	0.7		0.9		1.2	

Effect of adding urea to soil extract medium on the decomposition of Azolla. Tamil Nadu, India.

Induction of callus from leaf explants of *Azolla pinnata*

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Callus from root and leaf explants of *Azolla pinnata* var. *imbricata*, Jorhat strain, was induced on two standard media: MS (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) and SH (Schenk and Hildebrandt, 1972) as such and with certain modifications in type and concentration of the hormones and cytokinins. Callus induction from leaf explants was achieved in the modified SH medium supplemented with IAA (1.0 mg/ liter),

Callus induced from *Azolla pinnata*, after 8 wk in culture, Jorhat, India.